

ALPHA DELTA OVER! ?

Due to the mutation of the SARS CoV2 Alpha variant to the SARS CoV2 Delta variant, the Covid Pandemic is over.

The evidence.

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- 1) The mass roll-out of vaccinations against Covid19 is not the cause of the greatly decreased Case Fatality Rate (CFR) but can be better attributed to natural genetic viral mutation of SARS CoV2 from the Alpha to the much less virulent Delta variant.
- 2) The IFR of the Delta variant is about 5-10 times lower than the IFR of the Alpha variant and is estimated to be between 0.02-0.05% and is therefore many times milder than the seasonal flu. As a result, the pandemic must be explained over in countries where the Delta variant is dominant, thus removing the need to vaccinate anyway.

If vaccination were the reason for the sharp decline in the CFR, then there would be

- little or no difference in the CFR between Alpha and Delta and
 - a substantial decrease observed when a large proportion of the over-80s in England are double vaccinated
 - an even stronger decrease be observed if the majority of the over-60s are double-vaccinated. Decrease in this means decrease in "cases", "A&E visits", "overnight hospitalization" and "death"
 - a gradual decline in the CFR seen as more over-60s and over-80s are double vaccinated
- 3) The vaccinations are not effective against the Delta variant because the virus is so mild that effectiveness can never be demonstrated

Method:

To prove this claim, it is necessary to designate a country where both the Alpha and Delta variants are or have been dominant. That country must therefore have reliable statistical data. That country is England and the data comes from NHS and PHE (1, 2).

They use data from the laboratories with sequenced and geno-typical Covid. That is, PCR positive samples are tested in a laboratory for live virus and then genetically examined to determine the genetic variant. The weekly reports from PHE and NHS are not published on the same day or for the exact same period. This creates small discrepancies in the exact dates. However, this makes no difference to the calculations.

So contrary to the unreliable PCR test this data comes from the laboratory. On the basis of this data one arrives at a fairly exact Case Fatality Rate (CFR) instead of a rather indicative Infection Fatality Rate (IFR) which is based on the PCR test in particular and does not take into account, for example, the reason for hospitalization.

92.5% of deaths from or with Covid between March 2020 and July 2021 concerned elderly people over the age of 60 (80,474 of 87,455). England has 9,291,652 people over the age of 60, of which 2,836,050 are over 80 (1.2)

53% of deaths from or with Covid between March 2020 and July 2021 involved elderly people over the age of 80 aged 47,001 from 87,455) – (1.2)

96% of the deceased suffered underlying (1.2)

The **Delta** variant entered at the beginning of May with **509 cases** on **2 May rising to 33,207** on June 7 and **170,063** at the beginning of July.

The **Alpha** variant in the same period increased from **196,341 to 221,009** and then fizzled out at **225,864** at the beginning of July.

Vaccination began in England on 8 December 2020. PHE's technical briefings did not begin until early February 2021. Sequenced and geno-typed figures for Alpha were published. For this study, the period February to July 2021 is sufficient.

As shown in Table 1, on 28 March 2021, **41% of all 80+ were double-vaccinated** and on 18 April, 10 days before the first Delta cases, **83% of all 80+ were double vaccinated and 64% of all 60+ were double vaccinated.**

Thus, from March 2021 onwards, there should be a very substantial decrease in the CFR. The opposite is true (see Table 1 and Table 2):

March 28th:

- 151,344 cases (42,251 new to March 10, avg 2347 per day)
- 3.504 deaths (646 new since 10 March – avg 35.8 per day)
- CFR 2.32 CFR 1.53% for new cases

22 April:

- 185,216 (33,872 new to 28 March – avg 1,354 per day)
- 3,864 deaths (342 new compared to 28 March – avg 13.68 per day)
- CFR 2.08 and CFR for new cases 1.01%

May 2nd:

- 196,341 cases (11,125 new to 22 April – avg 1,112 per day)
- 4009 mortality (163 new compared to 22 April – avg 16.3 per day)
- CFR 2.04 and CFR for new numbers 1.47%

Table 1. – vaccination program

	27/12/2020	24/01/2021	10/02/2021	21/02/2021	10/03/2021	28/03/2021	22/04/2021	2/05/2021	7/06/2021	13/06/2021	21/06/2021	27/06/2021	4/07/2021
VACCINATIONS													
1 x vaxx all	786000	5792159	11422507	14930489	19587080	25915283	27516197	28760055	33622706	34666154	35901578	36927713	37656949
2 x vaxx all	0	440425	479320	510660	939323	2913596	8697109	12942168	23597409	25271379	26392701	27215158	28111379
1 x vaxx new		5006159	5630348	3507982	4656591	6328203	1600914	1243858	4862651	1043448	1235424	1026135	729236
2 x vaxx new		440425	38895	31340	428663	1974273	5783513	4245059	10655241	1673970	1121322	822457	896221
1 x vaxx 80+	524439	2590390	2962728	3017969	2689926	2699429	2699652	2699652	2699652	2699652	2699652	2699652	2699652
2 x vaxx 80+	0				445614	1158736	2361774	2525517	2525517	2525517	2525517	2525517	2525517
1 x vaxx 60+					11976296	12968672	13048291						
2 x vaxx 60+					531525	1779932	5968484						
1 x vaxx CEV					2010228	2053493	2074611	2088460	2108526	2110858	2108006	2116715	2118096
2 x vaxx CEV					128358	304192	1088932	1729280	2003615	2019285	2026234	2040312	2046244
1 x vaxx 16-64risk	0					5848381	6090514	6144818	6353917	6385903	6419471	6470878	6524919
2 x vaxx 16-64risk	0					0	848595	1648245	5281166	5595160	5780662	5888876	5964400
1 x vaxx 18+													37656949
2 x vaxx 18+													28111379
1 x vaxx 50	0				6169566								
2 x vaxx 50+	0								18998832		19571683	19653400	
1 x vaxx 50-	0					6368087							
2 x vaxx 50-	0					745707							

Note: the yellow boxes are the figures from the entry of the Delta variant

In the period 28 March to 22 April, we therefore see an increase in cases and mortality, while in that period the vast majority of the elderly and the weak are double-vaccinated. We do see a decrease in absolute numbers in the period just before the entry of the Delta variant, but it could also be explained by other reasons such as the entry of spring.

Vaccination as a causation for the absolute decrease seems imemmic as the CFR of the new cases remains at the same level as in the previous period. If vaccination had been the reason for the decline in absolute numbers, we should also have seen a constant decline in the CFR. There should also be a further decline after 2 May. However, a week later on June 7, we see an increase in cases and a sharp increase in CFR for Alpha.

What is also striking is that the CFR for the Alpha variant never falls below 1.89%. It should therefore be assumed that the Delta variant should start with a CFR of 1.47% to 2.08% upon its entry.

Table 2. - Alpha 2021

	27/12/2020	24/01/2021	10/02/2021	21/02/2021	10/03/2021	28/03/2021	22/04/2021	2/05/2021	7/06/2021	13/06/2021	21/06/2021	27/06/2021	4/07/2021
CASES													
cases all Alpha			50148		109093	151344	185216	196341	221009	224021	225085		225864
New					39884	42251	76123	11125	24668	3012	1064		779
cases 50+ Alpha fm 1/2/21											117263		
cases 50- Alpha fm 1/2/21											32289		
death all Alpha			1072		2858	3504	3846	4009	4196	4259	4262		4264
New					1786	646	988	163	350	63	3		2
death 50- Alpha											66		
death 50+ Alpha											1551		
CFR all Alpha total			2.14		2.6	2.32	2.08	2.04	1.90	1.90	1.89		1.89
CFR new cases					4.48	1.53	1.30	1.47	1.42	2.09	0.28		0.26
CFR 50-Alpha													
CFR 50+Alpha													

The period between 7 June and 21 June is the period in which the Delta variant becomes dominant and the Alpha variant extinguishes. The CFR for the Delta variant starts on 7 June with 0.1% and remains stable at 0.1-0.2%.

Where the Alpha variant retains a CFR of 1.4 to 2.09% after 2 May (except when extinguished with whole layers of absolute numbers), the Delta never exceeds 0.2% during the same period.

After 13 June, the number of infections in England will increase rapidly. From 33,207 cases on June 7 to 170,063 on July 4. In a month, Delta spreads faster than Alpha in 5 months in an almost fully vaccinated adult population. Table 3 for cases, ER visits, hospital admissions and mortality.

Table 3. – Delta

	27/12/2020	24/01/2021	10/02/2021	21/02/2021	10/03/2021	28/03/2021	22/04/2021	2/05/2021	7/06/2021	13/06/2021	21/06/2021	27/06/2021	4/07/2021
cases all Delta								509	33207	60655	92029	123620	170063
DELTA NEW CASES									32698	27448	31374	31591	46443
cases 0vax										35521	53822	71932	
cases 1x vax 21 days-									4094	6242	8562		
cases 1x vax 21 days+										9461	13715	17933	
cases 2x vax 14 days+										4087	7235	10834	
cases ttl vax										17642	27192	37329	
cases 50+ Delta fm 1/2/21											82458	111008	
cases 50- Delta fm 1/2/21											9571	12404	
A&E visit all Delta									851	1555	2406	4141	
A&E visits 0vax										1038	1571	2687	
A&E 1x vax 21 days-										116	186	301	
A&E 1x vax 21 days+										285	426	667	
A&E 2 x vax 14 days+										102	190	437	
A&E vax ttl										503	802	1405	
A&E visit 50-													
A&E visit 50+													
Onight all									223	488	745	1165	
Onight 0vax										324	484	733	
Onight 1x vax 21 days-										30	55	74	
Onight 1x vax 21 days+										87	115	162	
Onight 2 x vax 14 days+										40	80	173	
Onight vax ttl										157	250	409	
Onight 50-											564	852	
Onight 50+											181	307	

If vaccination were 95% efficient, these numbers should never occur. Although unvaccinated are twice as many cases as vaccinated, the rates are 2:1. On July 4, PHE reported 71,932 unvaccinated against 37,329 vaccinated, of which 10,834 were double vaccinated.

Half of all infections on 27 June were therefore vaccinated of which more than 25% were double vaccinated.

70,664 unvaccinated people are under 50, a group that represents only 3% of covid-related deaths.

If the substantially lower CFR for the Delta variant could be explained by vaccination then we should have observed a much lower CFR in mid to late April. A "jump" of 1.53 for Alpha on March 28, 1.01% on April 22 and then again to 1.47% on May 2 when Delta enters to 0.1% and remains for Delta cannot be explained by vaccination.

It is statistically detectable by viral genetic mutation.

Table 4 – Delta CFR

	27/12/2020	24/01/2021	10/02/2021	21/02/2021	10/03/2021	28/03/2021	22/04/2021	2/05/2021	7/06/2021	13/06/2021	21/06/2021	27/06/2021	4/07/2021
death all Delta									42	73	117	257	259
death all Delta New										31	44	140	
death Delta Ovax										34	44	92	
deat Ovax new											10	48	
death 1x vax 21 days-										1	1	1	
death 1x vax 21 days+										10	19	44	
death 2 x vax 14 days+										26	50	118	
death vax ttl										37	70	163	
deat vax new											33	93	
death 50- Delta											8	26	
death 50+ Delta											109	231	
CFR all Delta								0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.21	0.15
CFR Ovax Delta										0.10	0.08	0.13	
CFR 1x vax 21 days-										0.02	0.02	0.01	
CFR 1x vax 21 days+										0.11	0.14	0.25	
CFR 2 x vax 14 days+										0.64	0.69	0.66	
CFR vax ttl										0.21	0.26	0.44	
CFR 50- Delta													
CFR 50+ Delta													

What is striking about Table 4 is the significantly lower CFR for unvaccinated (Ovaxx) compared to the vaccinated. However, the main conclusion is of course CFR of 0.1% overall from the first results on June 13.

Finally Table 5

Table 5 – GOV.UK

	27/12/2020	24/01/2021	10/02/2021	21/02/2021	10/03/2021	28/03/2021	22/04/2021	2/05/2021	7/06/2021	13/06/2021	21/06/2021	27/06/2021	4/07/2021
GOV.UK													
CASES fm 01/9/20	1775135	2983064	3220495	3323338	3417998	3495577	3550901	3566758	3660273	3697411	3769121	3854057	4010001
NEW CASES		1207929	237431	102843	94660	77579	55324	15857	93515	37138	71710	84936	155944
DEATHS fm 01/09/20	27093	53241	66404	70736	73606	74960	75210	75314	75552	75598	75695	75771	75903
NEW DEATHS		26148	13163	4332	2870	1354	250	104	238	46	97	76	132
CFR new cases acc gov.uk		2.16	5.54	4.21	3.03	1.75	0.45	0.66	0.25	0.12	0.14	0.09	0.08
CFR basis gov.uk		1.78	2.06	2.13	2.15	2.14	2.12	2.11	2.06	2.04	2.01	1.97	1.89

In Table 5 of GOV.UK, which is based on PCR testing, we actually see the pattern we would like to see in PHE and NHS to at least see correlation between vaccination and greatly reduced CFR, let alone causation. After all, seasonal influence could also be used as causation if one wanted to analyze the GOV.UK figures.

It is clear that there is a correlation (with seasonal influence).

See chart 1 of "Our World in Data" on deaths per million in the EU in 2020 and 2021. These figures are also based on the PCR test and are about people who have died with or due to Covid19. There was no vaccination available in May 2020.

Chart 1

What is clear from the Gov.uk data, however, is that from the entry of the Delta variant, their CFR also drops to 0.1% and even lower. The higher the number of PCR Positive tests, the lower the CFR. On June 7th we started with a CFR of 0.25% on 93,515 new infections, a week later we arrive at a CFR of 0.08% on 155,944 infections. This is still a CFR, not an IFR. Extremely low.

On the day of writing 15 July 2021, the NHS reports 48,553 infections daily and 23 deaths, CFR or 0.05%.

Conclusion:

The figures from NHS and PHE do not in any way explain causation by vaccination. Even correlation is unlikely given the huge "jump" in CFR within a very short period in early June and the constant CFR around 2.0% for Alpha. The most likely explanation for the causation is the reduction of the virus by genetic viral mutation.

More contagious but less virulent.

According to John Ioannidis (3) the IFR was about 0.15% global in February 2021 during the Alpha variant. With a CFR of 0.08% at GOV.UK and 0.1% in PHE and NHS for the Delta variant compared to a CFR of 2.0% for Alpha, the IFR for Delta should be estimated at 0.02% - 0.05%. Similar to a cold.

Given the constant CFR for Alpha during the vaccination period especially between March and June, vaccination alone cannot explain the decrease in absolute numbers as they could also have been caused by seasonal influences.

With a CFR of 0.1% overall and even 0.0% for people under 50, vaccinations are not effective as less than 0.0% is not necessary. Less than 0.0% cannot be achieved and the Emergency Use Authorities were obtained because the benefits would exceed the risks. This is clearly not the case with the Delta variant.

- (1) <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/investigation-of-novel-sars-cov-2-variant-variant-of-concern-20201201>
- (2) <https://coronavirus.data.gov.uk/details/cases>
- (3) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33768536/>